

Potential Local Anaesthetics. Part VII. Synthesis of Diethylamino-Morpholino-Piperidino-N-(Substituted-1, 2-diarylethyl)-Acetamides

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N-1,2-diarylethyl)-chloroacetamides have been condensed with diethylamine, morpholine and piperidine to yield α -diethylamino-/morpholino-/piperidino-N-1,2-diarylethyl)-acetamides.

Diethylamino 2 : 6-dimethyl acetamide-xylocaine is the best known local anaesthetic among the basic amides¹. Out of several basic amides prepared in this laboratory α -piperidiny-N-(2,4-dimethylbenzyl)-propionamide and α -diethylamino-N-(2-chlorobenzyl)-acetamide were more active and less toxic as compared to Xylocaine². Diethylamino-N-(1,2-diphenylethyl)-acetamide has been patented as an anticonvulsant drug³. Zaheer *et al* reported basic amides from 1,2-diphenyl ethylamine exhibiting anticonvulsant activity⁴. With the object of testing them as local anaesthetics several basic amides have been prepared from 1,2-diaryl ethylamines.

Compounds No. 1, 2 of tables II, III and IV were tested for local anaesthetic activity and were found to be significantly active.

EXPERIMENTAL

1,2-Diaryl ethylamines were prepared from the corresponding ketones by Leuckart reaction as described by Nerlekar and Nargund⁵.

Condensation of amines with α -chloroacetyl chloride giving N-(1,2-diarylethyl)-chloroacetamides and replacement of α -halogen by secondary amines giving diethylamino-morpholino-piperidino-N-(1,2-diarylethyl)-acetamides was carried out as described earlier⁶. Compounds prepared are recorded in Tables I to IV.

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TABLE I

N-(1,2-diarylethyl)-chloroacetamides

No.	X	M.P. °C	Formula	% Nitrogen		% Chlorine	
				Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	120-122	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₂ NCl	4.4	4.6	11.6	11.7
2.	<i>p</i> -C ₂ H ₅ O	143	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ NCl	4.2	4.4	11.0	11.2
3.	<i>p</i> -C ₃ H ₇ O	120-124	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₂ NCl	4.1	4.2	10.5	10.7
4.	<i>p</i> -C ₄ H ₉ O	98-100	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₂ NCl	3.9	4.1	10.1	10.3
5.	<i>p</i> -C ₅ H ₁₁ O	125	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ O ₂ NCl	3.7	3.9	9.8	9.9
6.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	136	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ ONCl	4.7	4.9	12.10	12.3
7.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	125-128	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ ONCl	4.4	4.6	11.6	11.8
8.	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	145-147	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ ONCl	4.4	4.6	11.6	11.8
9.	<i>p</i> -Cl	134-135	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ONCl ₂	4.3	4.5	23.0	23.1

TABLE II

Diethylamino-N-[1-(alkyl/alkoxy/chlorophenyl)-2-phenyl ethyl]-Acetamides

No.	X	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	% Nitrogen	
				Found	Reqd.
1.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	95-96	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂	8.00	8.20
2.	<i>p</i> -C ₂ H ₅ O	86	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ O ₂ N ₂	7.70	7.90
3.	<i>p</i> -C ₃ H ₇ O	99	C ₂₃ H ₃₂ O ₂ N ₂	7.40	7.60
4.	<i>p</i> -C ₄ H ₉ O	86	C ₂₄ H ₃₄ O ₂ N ₂	7.20	7.30
5.	<i>p</i> -C ₅ H ₁₁ O	90	C ₂₅ H ₃₆ O ₂ N ₂	6.90	7.10
6. ⁴	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	91	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ ON ₂	8.40	8.60
7.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	62-64	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ ON ₂	8.10	8.30
8.	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	99-100	C ₂₂ H ₃₀ ON ₂	8.10	8.30
9.	<i>p</i> -Cl	110-112	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ ON ₂ Cl	7.90	8.10

TABLE III

Morpholino-N-[1-(alkyl-/alkoxy-/chlorophenyl)-2-phenyl-ethyl]-Acetamides

No.	X	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	% Nitrogen	
				Found	Reqd.
1.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	126–128	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₂	7.70	7.90
2.	<i>p</i> -C ₂ H ₅ O	142–143	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₂	7.40	7.60
3.	<i>p</i> -C ₃ H ₇ O	140	C ₂₃ H ₃₀ O ₃ N ₂	7.20	7.30
4.	<i>p</i> -C ₄ H ₉ O	133	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ O ₃ N ₂	6.90	7.10
5.	<i>p</i> -C ₅ H ₁₁ O	100–102	C ₂₅ H ₃₄ O ₃ N ₂	6.60	6.80
6.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	150–152	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂	8.10	8.30
7.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	110–112	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂	7.80	8.00
8.	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	132	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂	7.80	8.00
9.	<i>p</i> -Cl	116–118	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	7.60	7.80

TABLE IV

Piperidino-N-[1-(alkyl-/alkoxy-/chlorophenyl)-2-phenyl-ethyl]-Acetamides

No.	X	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula	% Nitrogen	
				Found	Reqd.
1.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	119	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ O ₂ N ₂	7.80	8.00
2.	<i>p</i> -C ₂ H ₅ O	115	C ₂₃ H ₃₀ O ₂ N ₂	7.50	7.70
3.	<i>p</i> -C ₃ H ₇ O	112	C ₂₄ H ₃₂ O ₂ N ₂	7.20	7.40
4.	<i>p</i> -C ₄ H ₉ O	110–112	C ₂₅ H ₃₄ O ₂ N ₂	6.90	7.10
5.	<i>p</i> -C ₅ H ₁₁ O	97	C ₂₆ H ₃₆ O ₂ N ₂	6.70	6.90
6.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	105	C ₂₂ H ₂₈ ON ₂	8.10	8.30
7.	3,4-(CH ₃) ₂	90–92	C ₂₃ H ₃₀ ON ₂	7.80	8.00
8.	2,5-(CH ₃) ₂	119–120	C ₂₃ H ₃₀ ON ₂	7.80	8.00
9.	<i>p</i> -Cl	105–106	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ ON ₂ Cl	7.70	7.90

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